

THE GENUS *LAPPULA* MOENCH IN THE FLORA OF THE TAMDY RELICT MOUNTAINS

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Abstract. This article provides data on new growth localities of species belonging to the genus *Lappula* Moench distributed in the Tamdy relict mountains. The studies were conducted in the Tamdy of the Navoi region between 2022 and 2025. Based on existing literature data and the results of field research, 9 species of the genus *Lappula* were recorded in the study area, of which five species (*Lappula patula*, *L. spinocarpos* subsp. *ceratophora*, *L. microcarpa*, *L. consanguinea*, and *L. spinocarpos*) are reported for the first time for this region.

Keywords: Kyzylkum, Tamdy, *Lappula*, relict mountain, flora, glochidiate spines corolla tube.

Introduction

Globally, the genus *Lappula* comprises 50–60 species and is the second-largest genus within the tribe Eritrichieae, following the genus *Eritrichium*. Members of the genus are distributed across Eurasia, western North America, North Africa, and Australia. Despite its broad geographical range, the center of diversity for the genus is considered to be Central Asia [2].

Lappula species are annual, occasionally biennial, or perennial herbs, covered with stiff or soft hairs, and possess blue or white funnel-shaped or bell-shaped corollas. Five distinct appendages are present at the apex of each corolla tube. Flowers are (almost) sessile or pedicellate; the pedicel sometimes elongates and curves downward during fruiting; sepals accresce with the fruit. Nutlets are arranged obliquely or vertically relative to the gynobase, often heterocarpic; nutlets are triangular-ovate to ovate in dorsal view, with a concave or, rarely, convex back. The margins of the fruit are surrounded by one or several rows of marginal prickles (spines), which are either free or fused to varying degrees. The fruit often features a membranous marginal wing formed by the united bases of transparent or glochidiate spines, which may be spread out or curved inward; in rare cases, nutlets are glabrous and firmly attached to the gynobase [8].

Species of *Lappula* were initially included within the genus *Myosotis* L., based on the similarity of generative and vegetative characters between the members of these two genera. In the late 18th century, J.E. Gilibert (1782) and Moench (1794) independently described the genus *Lappula*. Following the 20th century, the volume of research conducted on the genus increased significantly. Specifically, M.G. Popov (1953) reported in the "Flora of the USSR" that 44 species of *Lappula* existed, 21 of which were new to science at that time. He classified these species into two sections and 14 series. C.J. Wang (1981) categorized the *Lappula* species in China into two sections and seven subsections. In the recent past, S.V. Ovchinnikova (2005) recorded 70 species within the genus *Lappula*, organizing them into eight sections and 14 series. Despite the continuous taxonomic changes in the tribes of the Boraginaceae family over the last 100 years, the genus *Lappula* has been consistently included in the tribe Eritrichieae Benth. et Hook. since it was first described in 1876 [1].

Recently, S. Ovchinnikova (2006) utilized nutlet surface characteristics and pericarp ultrastructure to determine evolutionary patterns and phylogenetic relationships within the tribe Eritrichieae [5]. Subsequently, based on this data, she divided the genera within Eritrichieae into six subtribes (Ovchinnikova 2009). Based on the specific characteristics of the nutlets and pollen grains, she included the genera *Lappula* and *Lepechiniella* Popov as the sole members of the subtribe Echinosperrinae [6].

Modern research within the genus continues to this day [3, 4]. In recent years, intensive scientific work has been carried out on the modern re-inventory of the flora of Uzbekistan. According to the obtained data, 118 species belonging to 31 genera and 10 tribes of the Boraginaceae family have been identified in the flora of Uzbekistan. Of these, 28 species belong to the genus *Lappula* [7]. This information further underscores the significant position of the genus *Lappula* in the flora of Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods

The object of the research is the members of the genus *Lappula* Moench distributed in the flora of the Tamdy relict mountains. Scientific names of the species were verified using online databases such as POWO (www.plantsoftheworldonline.org), GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org>), and Plantarium (<https://www.plantarium.ru>). Morphological characters were determined using specialized scientific literature, including the "Key to the Plants of Central Asia" and the "Flora of Uzbekistan." Herbarium specimens were analyzed based on the collections belonging to the Tamdy Mountains stored in the National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH), Moscow State University (MW), and the Komarov Botanical Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (LE).

Results and Discussion

The Kyzylkum Desert, one of the largest arid regions in Uzbekistan, consists of sandy plains and relict mountain ranges rising between them. These relict mountains differ sharply from other desert landscapes of the region due to their distinct geological structure, edaphic factors, and strictly isolated ecological conditions. In modern scientific literature, the Kyzylkum relict mountains are recognized as unique natural areas where a number of rare and endemic plant species are preserved, as well as distinct centers of speciation. Therefore, analyzing the evolution of the vegetation cover of these areas, especially the deep study of their floristic composition using modern methods, is considered one of the urgent issues in botanical science. The Tamdy relict mountain range, chosen as the research object, also falls into the category of such unique areas with high floristic value.

The Tamdy relict mountains are considered a territory belonging to the Kyzylkum relict mountains botanical-geographical region within the Kyzylkum district (Tojibaev et al., 2016). The research area is located in the Tamdy district. The Tamdy district covers an area of 42.4 thousand km², making it the third-largest district in Uzbekistan and the second-largest in the Navoi region. Due to its territorial vastness, location in the Kyzylkum desert, and the surrounding relict mountains, the Tamdy district is rich in plant diversity. The flora of the region consists of desert and mountain elements. This serves as one of the primary reasons for conducting floristic research across the territory [9].

The Tamdy relict mountains possess a unique floristic composition, where rare and endemic species are widely distributed. This area is considered one of the regions with high floristic diversity in the Kyzylkum desert [12, 13, 14]. Furthermore, several species not previously recorded in the region were identified as a result of the scientific research conducted [10, 11, 15]. Field studies conducted between 2022 and 2025 recorded more than 310 species of vascular plants

in the region. Preliminary studies indicate that members of the Boraginaceae family occupy a significant position (27 species) in the research area. Within the family, the genus *Lappula* stands out due to its species richness.

Analysis of field studies and herbarium databases (TASH, MW, LE) revealed that 9 species of the genus occur in the flora of the Tamdy relict mountains. Among them, 5 species were recorded for the first time for the research area. Information regarding these species is provided below:

***Lappula patula* (Lehm.) Menyh.** «Tamdy district, Karatau relict mountain, 572 m a.s.l., 41.616911° 64.300600°. Small stony soils, 16.IV.2024. Sh.S. Fayzullayev». Ancient Mediterranean. Widely distributed on plains and in the lower mountain zone; occurs in fine-earth, stony, gravelly, and sandy soils. Weed.

Distribution: Europe, Asia, North Africa.

***Lappula microcarpa* (Ledeb.) Gürke** «Tamdy district, Karatau relict mountain, 18 km north-east of Zarafshan city, 505 m a.s.l., 41.642448° 64.399465°. Stony-gravelly soils, 07.V.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev»; «Tamdy district, 11 km north-east of Zarafshan city, 620 m a.s.l., 41.599649° 64.342903°. Gravelly soils, 07.V.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev»; «Tamdy district, 8 km east of Aktau relict mountain, 545 m a.s.l., 41.644179° 64.576841°. Small stony, gravelly slopes, 09.V.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev». Pontic–Ancient Mediterranean. Occurs on stony, gravelly, fine-earth, and loess soils, as well as on abandoned lands. Distributed in foothills and the lower mountain zone. Weed.

Distribution: Asia, Himalaya, Tibet, Siberia, Eastern European Russia.

***Lappula spinocarpos* (Forssk.) Asch. ex Kuntze** «Tamdy district, eastern side of Shushaktau relict mountain, 298 m a.s.l., 41.742437° 64.768530°. Stony slopes, 15.IV.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev»; «Tamdy district, Charikty, 12 km north-east of Zarafshan city, 420 m a.s.l., 41.666027° 64.287746°. Saline soils, 16.IV.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev». Mediterranean-Irano-Turanian. Grows in sandy, gravelly, and stony soils. Weed.

Distribution: Irano–Turanian, Saharo–Arabian, Mediterranean, South Asia.

***Lappula consanguinea* (Fisch. & C.A. Mey.) Gürke** «Tamdy district, northern slopes of Zimbiltau relict mountain, 718 m a.s.l., 41.524103° 64.437489°. Saline soils, 15.IV.2025. Sh.S. Fayzullayev». Euro-Siberian-Central Asian. Occurs in fields, abandoned lands, pastures, weed-infested areas, and around residential areas. Distributed on plains, in foothills, and in the lower and middle mountain zones. Weed.

Distribution: Europe, Asia, Siberia.

***Lappula spinocarpos* subsp. *ceratophora* (Popov) Y.J. Nasir (= *Lappula ceratophora* (Popov) Popov)** «Tamdy district, Kurgantau relict mountain, 586 m a.s.l., 41.511558° 64.296857°. Gypsaceous slopes, 16.IV.2024. Sh.S. Fayzullayev»; «Tamdy district, Yamantau relict mountain, 18 km south-west of Zarafshan city, 437 m a.s.l., 41.457356° 64.046536°. Gravelly slopes, 18.IV.2024. Sh.S. Fayzullayev»; «Tamdy district, western part of Aktau relict mountain, 380 m a.s.l., 41.668503° 64.423569°. Stony, gravelly soil, 22.IV.2024. Sh.S. Fayzullayev». Irano-Turanian. Grows in gravelly deserts, stony outcrops, variegated beds, and on gypsaceous and stony slopes. Used as fodder.

Distribution: Central Asia, Iran, Iraq, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia.

According to scientific research conducted in the Kyzylkum relict mountains in recent years, 8 species were recorded in the flora of the Sultanuvays relict mountain (R.Kh.

Yesemuratova, 2022), 5 species in the flora of the South-Eastern Kyzylkum relict mountains (A.R. Batoshov, 2016), and 3 species in the flora of Bukantau (G.A. Serekeyeva, 2011).

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of field research and data from the National Herbarium of Uzbekistan (TASH) as well as foreign collections (MW, LE), it was determined that 9 species belonging to the genus *Lappula* of the Boraginaceae family are distributed in the flora of the Tamdy relict mountains in the Navoi region. As a significant scientific novelty of the study, 5 species of the genus — *Lappula patula*, *L. spinocarpos* subsp. *ceratophora*, *L. microcarpa*, *L. consanguinea*, and *L. spinocarpos* — were recorded for the first time for this territory. The indicators of species diversity in the Tamdy relict mountains were found to be significantly higher compared to other regions of the Kyzylkum, specifically the flora of Sultanuvays (8 species), South-Eastern Kyzylkum (5 species), and Bukantau (3 species). The accumulation of new floristic data confirms that the flora of the Tamdy relict mountains is not yet fully studied and scientifically justifies the necessity of continuing systematic inventory work in the region.

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